

Integration of Nitrogen Recovery and Biogas Enrichment in WWTPs through Bioelectrochemical Technologies

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Abstract

The NIMBI project focuses on developing a bioelectrochemical system to recover nitrogen and upgrading biogas from wastewater treatment plants with anaerobic digestion. By leveraging organic matter degradation for energy, the system minimizes energy demand and eliminates chemical use. It extracts ammonia for biofertilizer production and enhances biogas quality by removing impurities, resulting in biomethane-enriched gas (>80% CH₄). With expected energy savings of 15% for organic matter treatment and recovery of 80% ammoniacal nitrogen from rejected water, the technology will undergo lab and pilot-scale validation, offering a sustainable solution for wastewater and biogas treatment.

Keywords

Bioelectrochemical system; Biogas upgrade; Municipal wastewater; Nitrogen recovery; Reject water

INTRODUCTION

Municipal wastewater contains high concentrations of nutrients, including nitrogen, which are traditionally removed in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) through processes such as nitrification and denitrification, without considering their recovery. Recovering nitrogen from WWTPs not only addresses pollutant removal but also supports a circular economy by transforming waste into valuable resources. Bioelectrochemical systems (BES) have emerged as promising, sustainable technologies for nitrogen recovery from wastewater due to their mild operating conditions and low energy and reagents demand. One of the applications of BES reactors is the hydrogen production in the cathode electrode, which increases the cathodic pH, shifting the ammonium/ammonia equilibrium toward the formation of the latest. The recovered ammonia can then be transformed into fertilizers, offering a practical and effective solution for agricultural applications, with demonstrated potential to support crop growth and productivity (Losantos et al., 2021; Rodrigues et al., 2022). Alternatively, physicochemical methods such as adsorption, membrane filtration, ion exchange, chemical precipitation, and ammonia stripping are more established, but face challenges related to operating conditions, high costs, reliance on energy-intensive processes, and the need for costly chemicals. Besides, the production of hydroxyls in the cathode chamber of BES system allows to capture of CO₂ from biogas, making BES a proper technology for biogas upgrading. However, despite the potential of BES against other technologies, its widespread application remains limited due to significant cost barriers, low kinetics and, particularly, those related to scalability and implementation (Farghali et al., 2024).

The NIMBI project proposes to increase the competitiveness of this technology through an innovative approach that integrates BES with ulterior ammonia stripping, utilizing biogas as the stripping medium. This novel combination simultaneously facilitates nitrogen recovery, biogas upgrading and efficient hydrogen production, presenting a synergistic solution to reduce energy costs and enhance the sustainability of wastewater treatment processes.

DISCUSSION

The NIMBI project aims to develop a BES reactor for nitrogen recovery in WWTPs with anaerobic digestion, while simultaneously upgrading the generated biogas (Figure 1). This innovative approach aims to address the current energy limitations of electrochemical systems by treating primary effluent as an anolyte to harness energy from the biodegradation process of organic matter, thereby reducing the total energy demand for nitrogen recovery. Electrons generated through organic matter (OM) oxidation, collected at the anode, will contribute to hydroxyls production at the cathode, causing a pH increase in the catholyte. The cathode is fed with anaerobic reject water rich in NH_4^+ , as catholyte, and the OH^- produced also in the cathode leads to the deprotonation of NH_4^+ into NH_3 , without the need for chemical addition. The resulting NH_3 will be extracted by stripping with biogas, simultaneously reducing the concentration of CO_2 (dissolved in basic media) and other impurities such as H_2S and siloxanes contained in raw biogas as they are retained in the catholyte, therefore enhancing the CH_4 content of the biogas. The resulting gas stream will be circulated through two membrane contactors: the first one for the further removal of CO_2 , leading to a biomethane-enriched stream ($>80\% \text{CH}_4$), and the second for the recovery of the stripped NH_3 as ammonium salt, a valuable biofertilizer. The NIMBI technology is expected to be competitive with current state of the art nitrogen recovery technologies, as it will demonstrate low energy consumption per kg of recovered nitrogen and by reducing the energy demand of WWTP by 15%—with 10% savings from OM degradation and 5% from nitrogen recovery—whilst enabling the recovery of 80% of total ammoniacal nitrogen contained in reject water. NIMBI process will be optimized with real effluents at laboratory-scale prior to its validation through pilot-scale at a WWTP.

Figure 1. Flow chart of NIMBI solution.

Three different WWTPs, were the candidates for the demonstration of the technology in the following years of the project, being Madrid (A, B) and Catalonia (C) WWTP, Spain. Two types of streams were explored, organic matter-rich streams and ammonia-rich streams, required for the operation of the BES. In the first case, effluent from the primary clarifier was considered, due to its high content of easily biodegradable OM and low solids content. On the nitrogen side, reject water coming from anaerobic digestion dehydrated digestate was considered (Table 1). Raw biogas from anaerobic digestion was also monitored.

Table 1. Average values of relevant parameters of the different streams considered.

	Primary clarifier effluent			Primary sludge			Reject water		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
Cond (mS/cm)	-	1.55	2.22	-	1.91	2.96	-	4.27	5.81
pH	-	7.28	8.3	5.57	6.06	6.15	7.57	7.38	7.77
DBO ₅ (mg/L)	266	303	200	-	9903	13013	-	201	99
COD _s (mg/L)	-	171	179	-	1166	1450	-	254	226
COD _t (mg/L)	502	563	446	-	27830	37076	1412	431	560
DBO ₅ /COD _s	0.53	0.42	0.46	-	0.36	0.35	-	0.47	0.18
N-NH ₄ ⁺ (mg/L)	46	35	45	-	60.74	106.12	829	430	510
N _t (mg/L)	75	59		-	-	-	-	-	-
P _t (mg/L)	9	16	17	-	71	64	199	167	49
TSS (mg/L)	137	437	148	4.75	2.17	2.48	265	226	244
VSS (mg/L)	-	436	110	3.98	1.48	1.64	154	56	146

Table 2. Average values of relevant parameters at the biogas stream.

	Biogas			Treated Biogas
	A	B	C	C
CH ₄ (%)	68.6	64.9	65.1	66.7
CO ₂ (%)	31.4	33.2	31.9	29.4
O ₂ (%)	-	0.3	0.8	0.7
N ₂ (%)	-	1.6	3.9	3.2
H ₂ S (mg/L)	79	68	403	34
Siloxane (mg/m ³)	-	-	0.77	-

BES reactors are based on a flat plate configuration (Figure a), with chambers of thickness about 10-30 mm. Due to this low thickness, BES are prone to clogging when fed with effluents containing high concentrations of solids; therefore, primary effluent should be considered as the main OM-rich stream to be used. This would leave primary sludge as an additive in case the OM content of the effluent was insufficient, to increase, when needed, the concentration of biodegradable organic matter in the effluent. Thereby, enhancing ammonium recovery capacity in the catholyte chamber of the BES without compromising the system.

Figure 2. (a) 2D-scheme of BES reactor with dimensions detailed in mm, (b) picture of the final assembled BES reactor and (c) scrubber column.

Regarding reject water, its low biodegradable organic matter and total suspended solids and high ammonia content, make it suitable as catholyte. In the case of biogas, only the C option had pretreated biogas by default, since the presence of siloxane can jeopardize the process. This last scenario was selected for the demonstration of the technology, using that pretreated stream. Furthermore, the rejected water from this site presents high conductivity and low content in organic matter, which is also advisable.

Based on the data collected from this analytical campaign, a lab-scale duplicate BES reactor and a scrubber column were designed and built (Figure b and c). The reactor consisted of two chambers, anodic and cathodic compartments, separated by a cation exchange membrane to hold the hydroxide ion in the cathodic compartment. In the anodic chamber, oxidation processes of the biodegradable OM contained in the primary clarifier effluent will occur. It will be catalysed by an electroactive biofilm attached to the surface of a carbon-based material (Sigracell® KFD 2.5 EA de SGL carbon), which will act as the bioanode. The electrons released during this oxidation will be transported to the cathodic compartment via the external circuit, where they will be used for water reduction to produce hydrogen and hydroxide ions in the cathode (Pt/C) and increase the pH of the medium as a result. The architecture for the chambers is hexagonal to mitigate gas buildup, leading to dead zones inside the compartment. Spacers have also been designed *ad hoc*, made of polyamide using 3D printing, with deflectors that promote the homogeneous distribution of the water fed to the reactor. In addition, a third current collector has been included that offers the possibility of incorporating a second anode, allowing the anode/cathode surface ratio to be studied to maximize the current demanded by the system and the production of hydrogen. Tests with synthetic electrolytes that imitate the main properties of the real primary clarifier effluent will be carried out. Once the system is stabilized and controlled with the synthetic effluent, tests will take place with real effluents. Gas complexity will also be gradually increased until the real biogas values are reached.

Finally, a scrubbing column for recovery of ammonia, with the dimensions and requirements in agreement with the BES performance, was also designed and integrated in BES reactor in a recirculation loop with the cathode chamber.

The campaign described and the results from the lab-scale testing will establish a base for the technological validation of the BES reactor, identifying the challenges to be addressed in terms of scalability and replicability of this innovative technology. By June 2025, the results of the lab testing phase will be available and reflected on, while the first steps of designing and building the pilot plant for the implementation in Catalonia will also be ready.

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